

obeyed Beer's law in the range 0.4–15 ppm of Cu^{II} , the optimum range⁸ being 2–11 ppm at 525 nm. The molar absorptivity was $4.6 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The photometric error was 2.7% following Ayres' equation.

Copper (6 ppm) was determined in the presence of many diverse ions. More than 100-fold excess of Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , UO_2^{II} , VO_2^{II} , Ti^{IV} , Al^{III} , In^{III} , Fe^{III} , Bi^{III} , As^{III} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Cd^{II} , Sn^{II} and Hg^{II} did not interfere. No interference was observed due to Fe^{III} , Bi^{III} , As^{III} , Mn^{II} , Pb^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} in the presence of 5 ml of 10% TEA. 25 ppm of Ag^{I} did not interfere. Except EDTA and cyanide with 30 ppm as tolerance limit, most of the anions did not interfere when present in more than 200-fold excess.

Determination of copper in alloy steel: Steel sample (0.5 g) was dissolved in 3M sulphuric acid (50 ml) and digested on a hot-plate with repeated additions of the acid. The solution was treated with a few drops of concentrated nitric acid for complete digestion. The clear solution so obtained was evaporated to a thick mass and then cooled, diluted with 50 ml water, filtered and washed with dilute acid. The filtrate and washings were cooled and transferred quantitatively into a 100 ml volumetric flask and volume made up to the mark. To an aliquot (5–10 ml) were added 0.1% reagent (5 ml) and 10% TEAHCl solution (5 ml) and pH was adjusted to 11.0. The volume of the solution was made up to the mark with requisite amount of ethanol and absorbance measured at 525 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of copper was found to be 0.32, 0.10 and 0.08% with a deviation of $\pm 0.01\%$ (certified: 0.32, 0.10 and 0.08% Cu in BAS steel).

Acknowledgement

The author gratefully acknowledges financial support from C.S.I.R., New Delhi, and a generous gift of BAS samples by Dr. R. A. Chalmers, University of Aberdeen, Scotland.

References

1. A. K. CHAKRABARTI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 489.
2. H. D. PORTER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 127.
3. A. RINGBOM, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1988, 115, 332.

Micro-determination of Rhenium with α -Mercaptobenzothiazole

SIRPAL KHAIRA (née SAIKHON) and L. R. KAKKAR*

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-132 119

Manuscript received 27 December 1988, accepted 17 May 1989

THERE are many chelating extractants¹ with sulphur atoms which can coordinate with metal ions. Sulphur containing organic compounds are still in use for extractive studies because of the coloured

complexes they form with the metal ions. Several sulphur-substituents of the oxygen of commonly employed chelating extractants have also been tried and their complexes are very often more strongly coloured and thus suitable for colorimetry. Recent literature survey reveals that such reagents have not received attention for the analysis of rhenium. The present paper reports an extractive method of determination of rhenium based on the formation of intensely coloured complex between the metal ion in its lower valent state and α -mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT).

Experimental

A standard stock solution of rhenium containing 1 mg Re/ml was prepared by dissolving potassium perrhenate (Specpure, Johnson Mathey) in water containing a few drops of dilute sulphuric acid, and lower concentrations ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared by appropriate dilutions.

Solutions of other ions were prepared by dissolving their commonly available sodium or potassium salts (B.D.H.) in distilled water. A 2% fresh solution of α -mercaptobenzothiazole (purified with alcohol) was prepared in acetone.

A 20% solution of stannous chloride (B.D.H.) was made in 1 : 1 HCl and diluted to 100 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of samples: Synthetic samples are prepared by mixing perrhenate and other metal ion solutions to get the desired composition.

Reverberatory flue dust samples from copper manufacture, containing no rhenium, were mixed with a solution of known rhenium content and dried in an oven. After fusion of the dust with sodium peroxide (8 times the weight of sample) the leach was neutralised with concentrated sulphuric acid and made slightly alkaline. It was boiled and the hydroxide precipitate was washed with distilled water. The filtrate was adjusted to 7 M HCl and rhenium determined as described below.

Procedure: To a solution containing $\leq 100 \mu\text{g}$ Re were added 10 M HCl (14 ml), 2% α -mercaptobenzothiazole (1 ml) and 20% $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution (1 ml) and the final volume was made up to 20 ml with distilled water. The solution was mixed gently, then allowed to stand for 10 min and the coloured species was extracted with 10, 10, 5 ml of chloroform equilibrating each time for 2 min. The combined solvent extract was filtered and made up to 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the orange coloured species was measured at 380 nm in 1 cm silica cells using a DU-2 spectrophotometer against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

In presence of stannous chloride, heptavalent rhenium is reduced to lower valence (IV, V) in acid solution which forms an orange coloured complex

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF Re-MBT ABSORBANCE* ON DIFFERENT PARAMETERS

HCl (M) ^a	0.10	2.00	4.00	5.00	6.00	6.50	6.75	7.00	7.50	7.75	8.00
Absorbance	0.020	0.065	0.070	0.110	0.200	0.210	0.225	0.230	0.230	0.225	0.220
MBT 2% (ml) ^b	0.40	0.45	0.55	0.60	0.70	0.80	1.00	1.35	1.50		
Absorbance	0.200	0.225	0.240	0.250	0.265	0.275	0.295	0.295	0.275		
SnCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O, 20% (ml) ^c	0	0.5	1.0	1.5	2.0						
Absorbance	0	0.295	0.295	0.295	0.295						
Standing time (min) ^d	5	8	10	12	15						
Absorbance	0.250	0.290	0.295	0.295	0.295						

*Conditions: ^aRe=100 μ g, MBT (2%)=0.5 ml, SnCl₂·2H₂O (20%)=1.5 ml, standing time=10 minutes, aqueous volume=20 ml, solvent volume=10+10+5 ml, number of extractions=3, equilibration time=2 min each, ^bHCl=7 M, other conditions same as in (a) excepting MBT, ^cMBT=1 ml, other conditions same as in (b) excepting SnCl₂·2H₂O, ^dSnCl₂·H₂O=1 min, other conditions same as in (c) excepting standing time.

with α -mercaptobenzothiazole extractable into chloroform whose absorbance is measured at 380 nm.

The formation and absorbance of the complex is influenced by the following variables. At 1 M HCl, the absorbance (0.02) of the rhenium complex increases considerably with the increase in acid concentration and reaches maximum 0.23 at 7–7.5 M HCl (Table 1). Hence 7.75 M HCl is recommended.

With 0.4, 0.45, 0.55 ml of 2% MBT, the absorbance values are 0.20, 0.225, 0.24 respectively (Table 1). For 1–1.35 ml, it has been found to be maximum at 0.295. In absence of a reductant, the absorbance is nil. On reduction with 0.5–2.0 ml of 20% SnCl₂·2H₂O, the absorbance is maximum at 0.295 (Table 1).

After addition of all the reagents and making up of the volume to 20 ml, the solution is allowed to stand undisturbed for 5 min, and absorbance value obtained after extraction is 0.250 which increases gradually with time (Table 1). For 10–15 min standing time, the absorbance of the complex remains constant at 0.295.

Four extractions with 6 ml of chloroform are necessary for quantitative transfer of rhenium complex into the solvent phase.

Optimum conditions: It is evident that for $\leq 100 \mu$ g Re: 7–7.5 M HCl, 1–1.35 ml of 2% MBT reagent, 0.5–2.0 ml of 20% SnCl₂·2H₂O, 10–15 min standing time for the development of colour and three extractions with chloroform (10+10+5 ml) equilibrating each time for 2 min, are the optimum conditions for the complete extraction of rhenium. The absorbance is measured at 380 nm after making up the volume to 25 ml against the reagent blank.

The complex is stable for 35 min and the results are reproducible. Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 0–4 μ g Re/ml with a molar extinction coefficient $14.880 \times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and Sandell's sensitivity $0.0125 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions on the absorbance of rhenium complex is studied. Sulphate (1.5 mg ml^{-1}) does not affect

the absorbance of the complex, whereas chloride (1 mg ml^{-1}) decreases it by 0.025. EDTA (0.5 mg ml^{-1}) and phosphate (25 mg ml^{-1}) increase the absorbance slightly in the same order. Tartrate (32.5 mg ml^{-1}) decreases it by 0.07. The presence of thiourea (25 mg ml^{-1}) seriously affects the absorbance. Metal ions (limit in paranthesis, mg ml⁻¹) such as Mo^{VI} (0.0325), W^{VI} (0.05), V^V (0.05), Bi^{III} (0.5), Fe^{III} (0.1), As^{III} (0.1), Ru^{III} (0.001), Co^{II} (0.25), Ba^{II} (0.25), Ni^{II} (0.05), Mn^{II} (0.02) and Fe^{II} (0.005) do not interfere. Cr^{VI} and Cr^{III} (0.05 mg ml^{-1}) interfere.

The method tolerates 7-fold excess of Mo^{VI}, and 10-fold excess of W^{VI}, V^V, Ru^{III}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, As^{III}, Bi^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Mn^{II} which seriously interfere in most of the existing methods of rhenium determination.

In the extracted species, the ratio of Re-MBT is found to be 1 : 2 as determined by Job's method of continuous variations² at three different wavelengths, i.e. 380, 410 and 450 nm, which is confirmed by mole-ratio method³.

Application: The usefulness of the method is further tested by its application to the analysis of flue dusts and several other samples containing rhenium in μ g amounts alongwith some important analytical elements in suitable proportions and the results are shown in Table 2. Also, the reagent

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF Re IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES BY THE PROPOSED METHOD

Sample no.	Sample composition		Re found μ g
	Matrix (mg ml ⁻¹)	Re μ g	
1.	Mo (0.75)	100	98
2.	W (1)	100	98
3.	Co (5)	20	19.5
4.	Fe (0.1)	50	50
5.	Ru (0.025)	100	98
6.	V (1)	75	75
7.	Fe (0.01), Bi (0.2), Ba (1), As (0.2)	50	49.5
8.	Mo (0.5), W (0.1), V (0.02)	80	80
9.	Mo (0.4), W (0.5)	100	98
10.	Fe (0.1), Ni (0.2), Co (0.3), Mn (0.1), V (0.3)	60	60
11.	Reverberatory flue dust (250)	25	25.5
12.	Reverberatory flue dust (150)	15	14.5

4-mercaptobenzothiazole has been used for the first time for Re analysis.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to the Chairman of the Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, for facilities. The authors are grateful to Prof. V. Yatirajam for helpful suggestions and to the Copper Corporation of India for the flue dust samples.

References

1. B. V. AGARWAL, S. P. SANGAL and A. K. DE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1965, 207, 256; H. AKAIWA and H. KAWAMOTO, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 40, 407; A. I. BUSEV and M. I. IVANYUTIN, *Tr. Kom. Anal. Khim., Akad. Nauk SSSR, Inst. Geokhim. Anal. Khim.*, 1960, 11, 172; E. Q. BERG and K. P. REED, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1966, 36, 372; YU. A. CHERNIKHOV and B. M. DOBKINA, *Zarod' Lab.*, 1949, 15, 1149; R. E. D. OLARK, *Analyst*, 1957, 82, 177; H. FISHER, *Mikrochem. J.*, 1942, 30, 38; M. KAWAHATA, H. MOCHIZUKI and T. MISAKI, *Bunseki Kagaku* 1962, 11, 1020; V. I. KUZNETSOV, J. BANKOVSKIA and I. LEVINS, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1958, 13, 267; H. MALISSA and S. GOMISCEK, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1959, 169, 401; A. T. PILIPENKO, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1953, 8, 286; K. I. SULAIMANOVA, N. P. ISMAILOV and Kh. R. RUSTAMOV, *Izb. Khim. Zh.*, 1982, 5, 78.
2. P. JOBS, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, 9, 113.
3. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.

Mercury Tris-[2,4,6-(2-hydroxy-4-sulpho-1-naphthylazo)]-s-triazine Trisodium Salt Complex in the Spectrophotometric Determination of Thiosulphate, Thiourea and Thiosemicarbazide Ions through Ligand Exchange Reaction†

ISHWAR SINGH*, PRATAP SINGH KADYAN
and
ASHOK K. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, M. D. University, Rohtak-124 001
Manuscript received 8 February 1988, revised 17 April 1989,
accepted 17 May 1989

TRIS-[2,4,6-(2-hydroxy-4-sulpho-1-naphthylazo)]-s-triazine trisodium salt (THT)^{1,2}, a water soluble heterocyclic azo dye, has been used in this work as reagent in the spectrophotometric determination of mercury(II). This azo dye forms two water-soluble complexes with mercury(II), a dark red in neutral solution and a blue in alkaline medium with high molar absorptivities making the present method

sensitive enough in comparison to other heterocyclic azo dyes used in the determination of mercury(II).

THT complex of mercury(II) has been further utilised as analytical reagent for spectrophotometric determination of thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide. The analytical principle incorporated is the ligand exchange reaction in solution, in which these compounds decompose the complex quantitatively to release the dye.

Experimental

A Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 2000 spectrophotometer with 10-mm matched glass cells was used for recording spectra and a Beckman pH meter was used for pH measurements.

A 1×10^{-3} M THT solution was prepared in double-distilled water; the solution was stable for several weeks. A standard solution of mercury(II) was prepared by dissolving metallic mercury in perchloric acid and was standardised gravimetrically³. Standard thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide solutions by dissolving appropriate amounts of analytical grade compounds in double-distilled water.

Phosphate buffer⁴ solution (pH 7.2) was prepared and 2 ml of this solution was used to bring the solutions for complexation reaction into the appropriate pH range.

Procedure :

Mercury(II) : To a suitable aliquot of sample containing 12–75 μg of mercury(II) add sufficient excess of THT solution (10 molar times) followed by phosphate buffer (2 ml) or to an aliquot containing 12–67.5 μg of mercury(II), excess THT (20 molar times) was added followed by 0.04 N sodium carbonate solution (4 ml). The solution was diluted to 25 ml with water and the absorbance measured at 550 nm or 633 nm against the reagent blank.

Thiosulphate, thiourea and thiosemicarbazide : To a solution containing 75 μg of mercury(II) was added 1×10^{-3} M THT solution (5 ml) followed by thiosulphate (0.2–1.57 ppm), thiourea (0.09–1.14 ppm) or thiosemicarbazide (0.11–1.27 ppm). The phosphate buffer solution (2 ml) was then added and diluted to 25 ml with water. The absorbance was measured against the reagent blank (5 ml of 1×10^{-3} M THT + 2 ml of phosphate buffer diluted to 25 ml). The difference between the absorbance of the complex before and after addition of thio compounds and the reagent blank is proportional to the concentration of the thio compounds.

Results and Discussion

Mercury(II) combines with THT to give two water-soluble complexes, a dark red in neutral solution having λ_{max} at 550 nm and a blue complex in alkaline medium having λ_{max} at 633 nm

†Presented at the Platinum Jubilee Session of the Indian Science Congress Association held at Pune, 1988.